

Electrocyclisations for Synthesis of Carbazoles and their Annulated Compounds

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Manuscript received 26 November 1993

The thermal- and photo-induced electrocyclisations of the hexatriene systems involving indole nucleus for synthesis of the pharmacologically interest carbazoles, and [a]-, [b]-, [c]- and [a,c]-annulated carbazoles are reviewed.

The thermal- and photo-induced 6π -electrocyclisations of hexatrienes for regio- and stereo-controlled annulation are of practical importance¹ and have been applied in efficient synthesis of natural products². Furthermore, the 6π -electrocyclisation followed by aromatisation has served organic chemists as a fundamental method of constructing benzene and its polycyclic derivatives. This methodology also provides an efficient approach to newer annulated heterocycles, when a heterocyclic ring bond participates in the

electrocyclisation. The triene systems involving the 2,3-double bond of indole nucleus for the synthesis of carbazoles are especially of major interest. Namely, many carbazoles and their annulated compounds possess important pharmacological properties and have been target compounds for synthesis, e.g. compounds listed in Chart 1³⁻⁵.

Therefore, the evolution of the electrocyclic-aromatisation methodology for the regiocontrolled

Chart 1

synthesis of polysubstituted and annulated carbazoles would offer an extremely attractive approach to this class of compounds. Thus, the subject of this review is the 6π -electrocyclisations of the hexatrienes comprising the indole nucleus, which are classified into five categories: the synthesis of carbazoles, and [a]-, [b]-, [c]- and [a,c]-annulated carbazoles.

Synthesis of carbazoles

Kano *et al.*⁶ first showed the synthetic potential of the electrocycloislation of 2,3-divinylindoles (13) for the synthesis of marine natural product hyellazoles (1). 2,3-Divinylindoles (13) were prepared from the indole (12). The electrocycloislation of the indole (13a) was carried out under refluxing in xylene (150°) in the presence of Pd-C as a dehydrogenation catalyst to give the carbazoles 15 and 16. The latter product may be formed

by liberating methanol from a primary intermediate (14) to aromatise. Use of decalin (210°) in this electrocycloislation could eliminate the undesired side-reaction. Similar heating of the 2,3-divinylindoles (13b,c) with Pd-C in decalin produced hyellazole alkaloids (1a,b). Recently, Hibino *et al.*⁷ have applied this methodology to the synthesis of carbazomycin (2). The 2,3-divinylindole (13d) was heated in *o*-dichlorobenzene (180°) with DDQ as the dehydrogenating agent to afford the carbazole (20) in 32.5% yield together with the by-product (19; 38.6%). In this case, even at higher reaction temperature, the yield of 20 would not be improved. The intermediate (18) seems to release methanol more readily than the intermediate (14) (Scheme 1).

Pindur and Adam⁸ attempted the electrocycloislation of 2,3-divinylindoles (23) bearing the elec-

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

tron-withdrawing group in the vinyl moiety. The 2,3-divinylindoles (23) were prepared by two methods: the Pd-catalysed vinylation of 2-formylindole (21) followed by Wittig olefination and the double Wittig reaction of 2,3-diformylindole (22) (Scheme 2). Heating of the 2,3-divinylindoles (23) in bromobenzene (156°) caused the cyclisation and 1,5-hydrogen shift to give the 1,2-dihydrocarbazoles (24) in 77–84% yields, which were readily converted to the carbazoles (25) by treatment with Pd-C. The thermolysis of 23 in the presence of Pd-C produced the carbazole (25) directly. In the case of 23b, additional elimination of CH₃CHO from the intermediate took place to form the compound 26. This cyclisation of 23 having electron-withdrawing groups may be smoother than that of 13 having electron-donating groups. This tendency is similar to that of the simple hexatriene systems^{1a,9}.

Electrocyclisation of the 2,3-divinylindoles (28), which were derived from the reaction of 2-vinylindole (27) with diethyl acetylenedicarboxylate (Scheme 3), cannot take place to degrade

Scheme 3

into polymeric material¹⁰. The authors have explained that the failure to effect the cyclisation resulted from the high stabilities of *transoid* conformation in 28, which could not convert to a *cisoid* one required for the cyclisation.

Juzt and Wagner¹¹ exhibited the electrocyclic conversion by elimination of an intermediary leaving group in place of dehydrogenation to aromatise. Thus, the desired 3-butadienyndoles (30) were

prepared by the condensation of indolylacetonitrile with the iminium compounds (29) (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

The butadienylindoles (30) were heated at 160° to cyclise smoothly, and then to eliminate dimethylamine from the cyclic intermediate (31) to give the carbazoles (32) in good yields.

We have synthesised hyellazole (1a) and demethoxycarbazomycin (21) using the electrocyclic cyclisation of 3-butadienylindoles (34) derived from indolin-3-one (33)¹². Thus, heating of the indoles (34) in decalin (196°) advanced the *E,Z*-isomerisation of the enol moiety, cyclisation, elimination of methanol, and desilylation to afford the 3-hydroxycarbazoles (35) in 40–60% yields. The *O*-methylation of 35a,b followed by *N*-deacetylation gave hyellazole (1a) and demethoxycarbazomycin (21), respectively (Scheme 5).

Treatment of 2-vinylindoles (36) with Vilsmeier reagent formed the intermediary iminiums (37), which on heating gave rise to tautomerisation, electrocyclic cyclisation and elimination of dimethylamine to afford the carbazole (39)¹³ (Scheme 6). In the case of 2-(1-substituted-vinyl)indole (36b,c), however, the reaction was not smooth, because the steric congestion of the substituent (R) may make it more difficult for 38 to form or to attain the proper conformation required for the electrocyclic cyclisation.

Flash pyrolysis (at 500°/0.05–0.1 mm Hg¹⁴

Scheme 5

or 600°/0.01–0.0011 mm Hg¹⁵) of the condensed product (42) of 3-formylindole (40) and meldrum acid (41) gave 2-hydroxycarbazole (45) in good yield (Scheme 7). The reaction pathway is as follows: the fragmentation of the dioxanedione ring generates the intermediary indolylmethyleneketene (43). The 1,5-hydrogen shift of 43 and the electrocyclic reaction of butadienylketene

Scheme 6

Scheme 7

(44), followed by the tautomerisation produces 45. Similarly, the pyrolysis of the adduct (47) obtained from 2-formylindole (46) afforded 3-hydroxycarbazole (48) in 82% yield¹⁵.

Danheiser *et al.*¹⁶ demonstrated the efficient annulation method for the regioselective synthesis of highly substituted aromatic compounds, and its application to the synthesis of the hyellazole alkaloid (1). Irradiation of α -diazoketone (49) with the acetylenes (51) at room temperature,

followed by heating of the resulting mixture gave the carbazole (54) in good yields (Scheme 8). This annulation includes many steps: the initial photochemical Wolff rearrangement of α -diazoketone (49) to generate the indolylketene (50); then 50 combines with the acetylene (51) in the regioselective [2+2]-cycloaddition to produce the cyclobutanone (52), which causes 4π -electrocyclic cleavage to form the butadienylketene (53). Further, the thermal 6π -electrocyclisation of 53 followed by tautomerisation proceeds to give the carbazole (54). The carbazole (54a) was converted into hyellazone (1a) by the cross-coupling reaction of the triflate of 54a with phenyltrimethylstannane. The authors have commented on the limitation that the normal acetylene such as 1-phenylpropyne or 1-hexyne did not function successfully in this annulation.

Synthesis of [b]-annulated carbazoles

The [b]-annulated carbazoles were prepared by the electrocyclic reaction of the corresponding orthoquinodimethane derivatives, e.g. 55 and 56 (Chart 2).

Liebeskind *et al.*¹⁷ demonstrated the general synthesis of carbazolequinone systems using the cyclisation of the orthoquinodimethanes. Thus,

Scheme 8

Chart 2

the indolylbenzocyclobutanones (**59**) obtained by the addition of 2-lithioindole (**57**) to benzocyclobutanones (**58**) were heated at 160° to give the benzo[*b*]carbazoles (**61**), which were converted to the quinone derivatives (**62**) in high yields. The annulation process involves the tandem pericyclic reactions: 4π -electrocyclic ring opening of **59** followed by 6π -electrocyclisation of the generated intermediary ketene (**60**) to yield the hydroquinone (**61**) after tautomerisation (Scheme 9).

Scheme 9

The flash pyrolysis ($400\text{--}410^\circ$, 5 min.) of 3-ethyl-2-vinylindoles (**63**) generated the intermediary indole-2,3-quinodimethanes (**64**) to cyclise to the carbazoles (**65**)¹⁸ (Scheme 10).

Scheme 10

The pyrido[4,3-*b*]carbazole system is pharmacologically important. Ellipticine (**5**), olivacine (**6**) and elliptinium (**7**) exhibit pronounced antitumor activities. Therefore, many synthetic approaches to this ring system have been reported⁴.

Bergman and Carlsson¹⁹ synthesised ellipticine (**5**) using the electrocyclic reaction of the intermediary indole-2,3-quinodimethane (**68**) as the key step. The pyridinium salt (**67**) was prepared by the condensation of 2-ethylindole (**66a**) with 3-acetylpyridine followed by the alkylation of the pyridine nitrogen with *n*-butyl bromide (Scheme 11). Rapid pyrolysis ($>350^\circ$, 5 min) of the salt (**67a**) gave ellipticine (**5**) in 72% yield together with its isomer (**70**; 10%). This thermolysis involves the following tandem reactions: 1,5-hydrogen shift of **67a**, electrocyclisation of **68**, dehydrogenation, and loss of *n*-butyl group. In contrast, slow heating (220° , 30 min) of **67a** afforded **70** as the predominant product. Although similar pyrolysis of the corresponding *N*-oxide also yielded ellipticine (**5**), the yield was low. In the case of the analogous adduct (**67b**) derived from 2-propylindole (**66b**), the

thermolysis did not occur smoothly resulting in a low yield of the ellipticine analog (69)²⁰.

Bergman's group²¹ also performed the short synthesis of olivacine (6) using similar electrocyclicalisation of the indole-2,3-quinodimethane (74) generated from 2 : 1 adduct (73) of 66a and pyridine aldehyde (72).

Kano's approach¹⁸ gave only ellipticine (5) without formation of an isomeric product such as 70 produced by Bergman's method. Thus, the 3-alkyl-2-vinylindoles (76) were obtained by treatment of the 2-lithio species of the indoles (75) with isonicotinic anhydride and Wittig reaction of the resultant ketones followed by deprotection at the nitrogen atom of the indole nucleus. Thermal reaction of 76 (500°, 3–7 min) gave ellipticine (5) and 11-demethylellipticine (77) in 50.2 and 60.4% yields, respectively (Scheme 12). The same group²² demonstrated an alternative method for the synthesis of ellipticine (5) and olivacine (6) using the electrocyclic reaction of the intermediary pyridine-2,3-quinodimethanes (79), which were generated by pyrolysis (450–500°, 3 min) of the 2-vinylindoles (78). In the thermolysis of 78c, ellipticine (5) and 11-demethylated

ellipticine (80) were obtained in 30.1 and 43.0% yields. The formation of the demethylated product (80) would be responsible for elimination of methyl group in the aromatisation step after electrocyclicalisation.

Synthesis of [a]-annulated carbazoles

Cyclisation of 1-aryl-2-(3-indolyl)ethylenes : The photocyclisation of 1-aryl-2-(3-indolyl)-ethylenes produced [a]-annulated carbazoles.

Irradiation of 3-styrylindoles (81) in the presence of iodine or air resulted in isomerisation and 6 π -electrocyclisation followed by dehydrogenation to give benzo[a]carbazoles (82)^{23,24} (Scheme 13). However, the yields of the carbazoles (82) were generally lower than those in photocyclisation of stilbene and its analogues^{1b}. The indole nucleus acts as a deactivating factor to this cyclisation. This is similar to the irradiation of 2-styrylpyrrole giving no cyclised product²⁵. On the other hand, the electron-withdrawing group in the olefinic moiety is desirable for the photocyclisation²³.

The pyrido[a]- and [c]-carbazoles are of interest in connection with the bioactivity of ellipticine

Scheme 12

(5). The oxidative photocyclisation of the indolylpyridylethylenes afforded the corresponding pyrido[*a*]- and [*c*]-carbazoles. The electrocyclic reactions for synthesis of pyrido[*c*]carbazoles are described in the next section.

Irradiation of 3-pyridylindole series (83, 85, and 88) under dehydrogenation conditions (using iodine or air) provided a variety of pyrido[*a*]-carbazoles, e.g. pyrido[3,4-*a*]carbazoles (84) obtained from 1-(3-indolyl)-2-(4-pyridyl)ethylenes

(83), pyrido[2,3-*a*]carbazoles (86) and pyrido[4,3-*a*]carbazoles (87) from 3-pyridyl derivatives (85), and pyrido[3,2-*a*]carbazoles (89) from 2-pyridyl derivatives (88), respectively^{23,26,27} (Scheme 14). The reactivities of 4-pyridyl (83a) and 2-pyridyl (88a) derivatives, when no substituent is on the olefinic moiety, are lower in their cyclisation compared to that of 3-pyridyl derivative (85a)²³. Further, attaching an electron-withdrawing group to the olefinic part tends to accelerate the annulation.

Scheme 13

Scheme 14

Irradiation of **83f** under nitrogen gave a different result from oxidative photolysis²⁸. Thus, the photoinduced cyclisation of **83a** initially took place to form the cyclised intermediate (**91**), which caused the prototropic shift to afford the dihydrocarbazole (**92**). The reaction was accompanied with the indole ring opening to produce the isoquinoline (**93**) and isoquinolino[6,7-*c*]quinoline (**94**). The oxidative photolysis of 1-(3-indolyl)-2-(2-furanyl)ethylene resulted in decom-

position, because of the sensitivity of the furan ring toward the photo-oxidation²³.

The indole[2,3-*a*]carbazole framework is incorporated in bioactive natural products such as staurosporine (**9**), rebeccamycin (**10**) and arcyriaflavins (**11**)⁵. Synthesis of this framework has been performed by thermal- and photo-induced electrocyclic reactions.

Eckhardt's group²⁹ has shown the acid catalysed

electrocyclisation of arcylriarubin C (95) to arcylriarubin C (11c) (Scheme 15). This suggests that

Scheme 15

the cyclisation is involved in the biosynthetic route of the indolocarbazole alkaloids. Therefore, this cyclisation has been used in synthesis of the indolocarbazole alkaloids by several groups.

Treatment of the bisindolyethane (97) with tert-butyl hypochlorite generated the intermediary ethylene (98) to cyclise thermally to indolo[2,3-*a*]-carbazole (99)³⁰. The starting ethane (97) was prepared from β-indole acetate (96) by gramine alkylation (Scheme 16).

Scheme 16

The dehydrogenation of the bisindolyethane

derivatives (100) to the ethylenes (101) was performed using DDQ in high yields³¹. The

Scheme 17

thermal electrocyclic reaction of bisindolylmalenic anhydride (**101a**)³¹ and maleimide (**101b**)^{32,33} to the corresponding indolo[2,3-*a*]carbazole (**102**) was effected in high yields with a mixture of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid and DDQ in refluxing chlorobenzene. Similar treatment of the ethane derivatives (**100a,b**) gave directly **102a,b** in 90 and 80% yields, respectively³¹ (Scheme 17).

Scheme 18

Kaneko *et al.*³⁴ synthesised rebeccamycin (**10**) using the electrocyclic reaction of **104** as the key step. The starting bisindolyl maleimide (**104**) was obtained by the coupling of indolyl magnesium iodide with dibromomaleimide (**103**). The cyclisation of **104** using silver oxide as an oxidising

reagent afforded the chromophore (**105**) of rebeccamycin (**10**). This cyclisation also was achieved by the irradiation of **104** in the presence of iodine and air.

The aglycon (**107**) of staurosporine (**9**) was obtained by the photocyclisation of **106b** derived from triptamine, while the cyclisation of its diacetate (**106a**) did not take place³⁰.

Rawal *et al.*³⁵ showed an efficient procedure for the annulation of stilbenoids containing electron-rich heterocycles to be unstable to photo-oxidation. Thus, the Pd-C mediated photolysis of 1-(3-indolyl)-2-(2-pyrrolyl)ethylene (**108**) with triethylamine and *p*-nitrobenzoic acid as a powerful dehydrogenating reagent in refluxing acetonitrile was carried out to afford pyrrolo[3,2-*a*]carbazole (**109**) in high yield (Scheme 18).

Recently, Marchesini's group³⁶ has demonstrated the non-oxidative photocyclisation of 2-aryl-1-(3-

Scheme 19

indolyl)ethylenes, which place a leaving group at the terminal of the hexatriene moiety. This method could be applied to the cyclisation of photo-oxidation-sensitive trienes. Thus, irradiation of **110** caused *E,Z*-isomerisation, 6π -cyclisation and aromatisation with elimination of ethanol and carbon dioxide to afford the corresponding [*a*]-annulated carbazoles (**111**) in good yields. Similar cyclisation of **112** also has been demonstrated as outlined in Scheme 19³⁷.

Cyclisation of 2-aryl-3-vinylindoles :

The photolysis of 2-phenyl- and 2-pyridyl-3-spiroindoles (**116**), which were prepared by the cycloaddition of 3-diazo-3*H*-indoles (**114**) to olefins (**115**), under nitrogen, produced benzo[*a*]- and pyrido[2,3-*a*]-carbazoles (**119**), respectively³⁸. The annulation arose from the following tandem reactions: the ring opening of the cyclopropane moiety to form 2-aryl-3-vinylindole (**117**), the photo-induced electrocyclic cyclisation of **117**, [1,5]-hydrogen shift, and dehydrogenation. In a similar manner, isolated 2-phenyl-3-vinylindole (**117a**) was irradiated to give **119a** and its dihydro derivative (**118a**) in 32 and 23% yields, respectively (Scheme 20).

Synthesis of [*c*]-annulated carbazoles

The photo-induced electrocyclic cyclisation of a 2-aryl-1-(2-indolyl)ethylene series provided [*c*]-annulated carbazoles in a similar manner as that above. Thus, the oxidative irradiation of 2-styrylindole (**120**) gave benzo[*c*]carbazole (**121**) in 67% yield³⁹ (Scheme 21).

Similarly, 1-(2-indolyl)-2-(4-pyridyl)ethylenes (**122**) were irradiated in the presence of iodine to give pyrido[4,3-*c*]carbazoles (**123**) in moderate yields³⁹⁻⁴¹. The irradiation of *trans*-(**122a**) under nitrogen resulted in isomerisation to its *cis*-isomer, which is unstable toward heat and reverts readily to *trans*-(**122a**) without cyclisation⁴¹. In contrast, *cis*-2-pyridyl derivative (**124a**) was obtained in the photolysis of *trans*-(**124a**) because of stabilisation with the intramolecular hydrogen bonding⁴¹. Prolonged irradiation of both *trans*- and *cis*-(**124**)

Scheme 20

under oxidative conditions yielded the pyrido[2,3-*c*]carbazoles (**125**)^{39,40,42}. In the case of 3-pyridylethylenes (**126**), pyrido[3,2-*c*] (**127**) and [3,4-*c*]carbazoles (**128**) were obtained^{39,40,43}. In contrast, the photocyclisation of **126b** under nitrogen advanced the pyridine ring opening of an initially cyclised product to yield the carbazole (**129**)⁴³.

Synthesis of [*a,c*]-diannulated carbazoles

The irradiation of 2,3-diphenylindoles (**130**) with iodine gave rise to cyclisation to yield dibenzo[*a,c*]carbazoles (**131**) in good yields^{44,45}. In the case of *N*-methyl- (**130g**) and *N*-phenylindoles (**130h**), similar cyclisation took place to afford **131g,h** together with oxidised products **132g,h** and **133g,h**⁴⁴. The latter product (**133h**) was also obtained by the photo-oxidation of the carbazole (**131h**). Photolysis of the indoles (**130**) having an electron-withdrawing group such as acetyl or nitro group caused mainly photo-oxidation to produce the corresponding benzamidobenzophenones (**132**)⁴⁴ (Scheme 22).

Conclusions : The thermal- and photo-induced

Scheme 21

6 π -electrocyclisation of the hexatrienes involving indole nucleus followed by aromatisation has furnished regioselectively a number of polysubstituted carbazoles and annulated carbazoles, including bioactive carbazole alkaloids. The

aromatisation step utilises the following two procedures: dehydrogenation and elimination. The electrocyclicdehydrogenation method, in some cases, produced a dihydrocarbazole together with the desired carbazole because of the stability

Scheme 22

of the dihydrocarbazole towards the dehydrogenating reagents. The loss of the substituent from the intermediary dihydrocarbazole rarely appears to give an undesired carbazole. In contrast, the electrocyclic-elimination procedure using the higher oxidation state trienes, which has the leaving group or the ketene moiety at the terminal position, is more effective as shown recently in several reports. With the use of the latter methodology the synthesis of structurally more complex carbazoles can be expected in future.

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